

THE CONCEPT OF NEGOTIATIONS ON CONCLUDING A CONTRACT IN CIVIL LAW, THE CHARACTERISTICS OF PRE-CONTRACT RELATIONS.

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ABSTRACT

In civil law, negotiations on the conclusion of a contract are the process of discussing the terms and agreeing on the details of a future contract between the parties. This process is considered a pre-contractual stage and may include discussion of the price, deadlines, liability of the parties, and other essential terms of the contract.

Basically, negotiations on the contract will be aimed at reaching a mutually acceptable agreement between the parties and creating a legally binding document regulating their relations. Successful negotiations require mutual understanding, respect for the interests of each party, and clarity of conditions to prevent potential future conflicts.

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Access

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Indeed, in the science of civil law, there are different views on the understanding of pre-contractual legal relations, which creates certain difficulties in forming a unified and precise definition of this category. Different concepts and theories may offer different approaches to analyzing and understanding pre-contractual relationships.

¹ Шполтаков О.В. Преддоговорные правоотношения: вопросу о понятии и юридической сущности/Власть закона. - No 2 (14), 2013. – С. 196 - 210.

V.V. Bogdanov defined the concept of pre-contractual relations as follows: "the main goal of these pre-contractual relations is the preparation for other relations arising in the future, that is, the preparation for civil law contracts."

Also, the researchers noted that in legal literature, the question of at what point the legal relations arising before the contract arise remains unclear.

Most scholars believe that only two stages play a role in the process of concluding a contract: offer and acceptance. Pre-contractual communication actions arise at the offer stage, and the resolution of pre-contractual disputes is included in the acceptance.

A number of other scholars believed that relations arising before a contract begin during negotiations between the parties. A.N. Kucher emphasized the impossibility of determining the exact time of the emergence of pre-contractual legal relations.

From the foregoing, we can conclude that pre-contractual legal relations consist of the process of agreement and discussion of the terms of the contract by both parties when concluding a contract.

Despite various views, the science of civil law strives to search for common principles and approaches to pre-contractual legal relations that can be applied in all situations. It should be taken into account that different concepts and theories can complement each other and offer different aspects of understanding this category, which ultimately contributes to a deeper and more comprehensive analysis of pre-contractual relations.

Subjects conducting negotiations on the conclusion of a contract in civil law are persons expressing the will to conclude a contract, in particular, individuals or legal entities with civil capacity. Subjects of pre-contractual relations can also be considered both the parties to the future contract and third parties participating in negotiations as intermediaries or representatives.

The object of the institution of negotiations on the conclusion of a contract is the legal relationship, which includes all the conditions and essential elements of the future contract, discussed and agreed upon between the parties. This may also be expressed in the subject of the contract, its price, term of execution, liability of the parties, and other conditions that determine the rights and obligations of the parties under the contract.

The legal institution of contract negotiation includes the process of discussing and agreeing on the terms of a future contract between the parties. Within the framework of this institution, the parties will have the right to freely express their will, protect their interests, receive information about the contract, and discuss all issues related to its conclusion.

According to legal sources, for pre-contractual relations to become legal force, it is necessary to determine the parties to such legal relations. For example, if the conclusion of a contract becomes mandatory for one party, it accepts the submitted proposal without any conditions or negotiations, and from this moment, mutual rights and obligations begin to arise between the parties. If the parties are free to conclude a contract, the emergence of legal relations between them will be different. That is, if one party sends an offer containing all the terms of the contract, the other party can not only agree to that offer but also send acceptance with other terms, and as a result, interesting, controversial negotiations about concluding the contract begin to arise between the parties.

Therefore, in our national legislation, it is advisable to analyze the issue of pre-contractual negotiations in a state of freedom of the parties in concluding a contract or in an accession agreement, public contracts.

As mentioned above, according to many scholars, the contract formation process consists of the offer and acceptance stages. According to Article 367 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an offer is a sufficiently clear proposal addressed to one or more specific persons, expressing the intention of the person making the proposal to consider themselves to have concluded a contract with the person to whom the proposal is addressed

and who will receive it. The offer must express the essential terms of the contract. An offer connects the person who sent it with the person to whom the offer is addressed, from the moment they receive the offer.

As can be seen from this definition, an offer, i.e., sending a proposal to conclude a contract, is also a type of pre-contractual negotiation process for concluding a contract. However, not every proposal to conclude a contract is considered an offer. To be an offer, it must possess a number of specific characteristics. For example, a proposal to conclude a contract must be addressed to a specific person or a certain circle of persons, and if the proposal is addressed to an indefinite circle of persons, we can consider it as an invitation to a public offer.

This proposal must also clearly express the intention and will of the person who sent the offer to conclude a contract with the person who will receive it. The contract must also specify the essential terms of the offer.

In addition, paragraph 4 of the Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Economic Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 18.12.2009 No. 203 "On Some Issues of the Application of the Norms of Civil Legislation Regulating the Conclusion, Amendment, and Termination of Economic Contracts" establishes that the process of concluding a contract consists of two stages: the first stage is called an offer, the second - acceptance. The party offering the contract is considered the offeror, and the party accepting the offer is the acceptor. This decree stipulates that not every proposal to enter into contractual legal relations is recognized as an offer, that the proposal must be sufficiently clear to meet the characteristics of the offer and clearly express the person's intention to conclude the contract, contain all the essential terms of the contract and be sent to one or more specific persons, and that the absence of any of the above features in the proposal should be considered by the courts as an invitation to make an offer.

The response of the person to whom the offer is addressed regarding its acceptance is considered acceptance. The appendix must be complete or complete.

Thus, based on the above provisions, we can say that in the judicial practice of our national legislation, the process of concluding a contract, as reflected in the theories of many scholars, consists of the stages of offer and acceptance.

In addition, in our civil legislation, there are such concepts as a public contract and an accession agreement. It is also advisable to discuss the legal nature of these types of contracts. After all, before entering into these types of contractual relations, the parties encounter issues of pre-contractual negotiations.

In our national legislation, the public contract is regulated by Article 358 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A public contract is one of the most common types of contracts. Examples of public contracts include passenger transportation by public transport, citizens' access to medical services, communication services, energy services, hotel services, and others. In most cases, a legal entity acts as a mandatory party to public contracts. However, individuals and legal entities can be individuals who may demand the conclusion of a public contract.

One of the most important features of a public contract is that the price of goods, works, services, as well as other terms of the public contract, are predetermined for all consumers.

Result

In the above provisions, we have repeatedly emphasized that entering into contract negotiations means initiating the process of discussing the terms and details of a future contract between two or more parties. This stage is considered the stage preceding the signing of the contract and includes discussion of all essential terms, including the terms on the subject of the contract, the price, the issue of deadlines, the terms of performance, the

responsibilities of the parties, and other important aspects. Negotiations usually begin after the parties have expressed interest in concluding a contract and are ready to discuss its terms.

In civil legislation, the accession agreement is one of the forms of concluding a contract. This means that the party that joins this agreement joins the agreement that already exists between the other parties. In this case, the acceding party assumes all the conditions and obligations stipulated in the preliminary agreement. The terms of the accession agreement are always predetermined by one of the parties to the agreement proposing the conclusion of the agreement. Examples of accession agreements include agreements on the use of utilities, communication, hotel, and transport services.

In other types of contracts, the parties enter into negotiations on the terms of the contract before concluding the contract, and if the parties can agree, conclude the negotiation process with the conclusion and signing of the contract. The terms of the accession agreement may be either fully accepted or fully rejected by the other party, and no protocols of objections or disagreements shall be drawn up against it. Accession to the proposed contract means acceptance of all the terms of the contract set forth in the form or other standard forms. However, in the process of concluding other types of contracts, the parties can enter into negotiations as many times as they wish.

Therefore, the main types of contracts concluded in the sphere of contractual legal relations are distinguished, which determine their essence and characteristics. We have analyzed that one of the types of contractual legal relations is free contractual legal relations and binding legal relations.

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